

TO THE JUDGE'S OFFICE FOR THE 6TH COMMERCIAL COURT OF FIRST INSTANCE

EXPERT WITNESS REPORT

FILE NO : 2021/ 66 Instruction
ASSESSMENT REQUESTED BY : Spektral Holding B.V.
REPRESENTED BY : Attorney Ayşe Nur Pamukçu
SUBJECT-MATTER : Value Assessment

In the lawsuit petition dated 15.09.2020, submitted to the Court by the Attorney of the Party requesting assessment, it was stated that a request was made for the assessment of current market value of the company named Anadolu Kalsit A.Ş. that was owned by the client company in order to be used in the transfer of that company or as evidence in the potential future disputes; according to this request, SMMM Arife Sinaç was appointed as expert witness with the decision dated 18.09.2020 taken by Çeşme Civil Court of First Instance under the case file numbered 2020/293 D.İş.; in the report issued on 09.11.2020 by that expert witness, it was stated as follows:

This company was based in Ankara and registered with Ankara Trade Registry Office; its capital was equal to TL 3.000.000,- and its primary area of activity was mining; the company opened a branch in Erzurum on 20.12.2011;

As of 09.06.2020, the company was structured as a joint stock company owned by the sole shareholder named Mas İlaç Yatırım A.Ş.;

According to the trial balance dated 30.06.2020 of Anadolu Kalsit Madencilik A.Ş., it was determined that company's capital was equal to TL 3.000.000,-; part of TL 2.372.500 of this capital was not paid; the company's net worth as of 30.06.2020 was equal to a negative amount of (-) TL 398.318,18 after taking into account accumulated losses and loss of the period;

An additional report dated 02.02.2021 was issued as a result of the objection made to the previous report and it was shortly stated in this report that examinations were made according to the book records since the engineering report submitted to the case file could not be reviewed because it was outside the area of expertise of the expert witness.

As already mentioned in the lawsuit petition submitted to the Court by the Plaintiff's attorney, it was determined that Anadolu Kalsit Madencilik A.Ş. that was owned by the requesting company named Spektral Holding B.V. had a capital of TL 3.000.000,- and all of this capital belonged to the company named Mas İlaç Yatırım A.Ş.

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(1)

It was further determined upon review of the documents included in the case file that there was one phenological report dated 18.06.2020 and numbered 74332, which was prepared by Assistant Professor Nurullah Hanilci and Assistant Professor Namık Aysal from the Engineering Faculty of Cerrahpaşa Rector's Office attached to Istanbul University in order to determine the calcite resource potential of the registered areas with access numbers 3074415 and 3249915 which were located in HACILAR and KARAKOÇ VILLAGES (PAZARYOLU-ERZURUM) and as a result of reviewing this report, it was determined as follows:

The registered areas numbered 3074415 and 3249915 remained in the district between Erzurum and Rize and these registrations was owned by Anadolu Kalsit Madencilik A.Ş.;

Potential calculations for the calcite resources available in both of the registered areas having operational license was made according to 2 different approaches by using "serial geological lateral sections method" and according to these calculations:

- Calcite resource available in the registered area having operational license and access number 3074415 was calculated as 2.138.355 tons according to the 1st approach and as 2.024.813 tons according to the 2nd approach,
- Calcite resource available in the registered area having operational license and access number 3249915 was calculated as 1.957.875 tons according to the 1st approach and as 1.724.813 tons according to the 2nd approach,
- According to the area (196.199 m²) calculated by the Global Mapper program, after taking into account outcropping calcite sites available in the registered areas with access numbers 3074415 and 3249915 without considering the operational license, calcite resource-potential was determined to be 9.809.950 tons based on a minimum calcite thickness of 20 meters or to be 14.714.925 tons based on a minimum calcite thickness of 30 meters (with calcite's specific weight taken as 2.5 gr/cm³),
- It was recommended that a geophysical study be conducted (Multi electrode Electric Resistivity Tomography – ERT) and data be obtained from a minimum depth of 50-70 meters with profile lengths of 300-350 meters so that resource-potential calculated with these registered areas could be transformed into a reserve,
- It was further recommended that after this geophysical study drills be made with intervals of 50 meters on each profile alongside total 4 profiles positioned with intervals of 50 meters at the north-side direction (running parallel to the slope) and in this case, in the registered area with access number 3074415, total 15 drills were recommended and in the registered area with access number 3074415, total 24 drills were recommended alongside 6 profiles. However, in order to plan both the geophysical study and drills mentioned above, topography maps scaled 1/1000 must be developed for the calcite sites in the registered areas and since the bent of the slope increases towards east in the calcite outcropping area, it seems that it will restrict the opening of access roads needed for these drills.

1/1000 ölçekli topografya haritaları oluşturularak planlanmasının yapılması, kalsit mostra alanında yamaç eğilimin doğuya doğru artması sondaj çalışmaları için gerekli yol çalışmasını sınırlandıracak şekilde gözükmemekte olduğu,
Belirtildiği anlaşılmaktadır.

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(2)

Ayrıca 3074415 ve 32499125 erişim nolu ruhsat sahalarındaki kalsit mostralarının jeolojik kaynak raporlamasına karşılık yüzey alan görünür değer tespiti açıklamasında da 30 m. Kalsit kalınlığına göre 14.714.925 ton civarında olduğu, ortalama fiyat aralığı 20-24 USD/TON olarak görüldüğü, ortalama 22 USD/ton yani 19,8 Euro/ton olarak hesaplandığında ruhsat sahaları toplamı 164,35 Hektar izinli ruhsatlı sahaların toplamı ise 21,22 Hektar dikkate alınarak 14.714.925 ton x 19,8 Euro dikkate alındığında 292 Milton Euro lık bir değere sahip olduğu, ancak bu hesaba ise de işletme maliyetinin dahil olmadığı belirtilmiştir.

NETİCE: Rapor içeriğinde de ifade edildiği üzere 3074415 ve 32499125 erişim nolu ruhsat sahalarındaki kalsit mostralarının jeolojik kaynak raporlamasına karşılık yüzey alan görünür değer tespiti açıklamasında da 30 m. Kalsit kalınlığına göre 14.714.925 ton civarında olduğu, ortalama fiyat aralığı 20-24 USD/TON olarak görüldüğü, ortalama 22 USD/ton yani 19,8 Euro/ton olarak hesaplandığında ruhsat sahaları toplamı 164,35 Hektar izinli ruhsatlı sahaların toplamı ise 21,22 Hektar dikkate alınarak 14.714.925 ton x 19,8 Euro dikkate alındığında 292 Milton Euro lık bir değere sahip olduğu, görüş ve kanısında olduğumuz iş bu rapor sayın mahkemeye saygılarımızla arz olunur.

Dr. Hasan KARADENİZ
Yeminli Adli Mali Bilirkişi

MÜSTEDİNATTIR
TEK BAŞINA
KULLANILAMAZ

Sefa ÖNTÜRK
Maden Mühendisi
T.C.
ÇEŞME
ASLİYE HUKUK MAHKEMESİ

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ASLİ GİBİDİR
1 Haz. 2021
Poİat İEKİN
Yazı İşleri Müdürü

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02 Haziran 2021

(2)

As compared to the geological resource reporting of the calcite outcrops available in the registered areas with access numbers 3074415 and 32499125, in the visible asset determination made according to the surface area, calcite resource was given as 14.714.925 tons based on a calcite thickness of 30 meters; average price range was determined to be 20-24 USD/Ton; if we take the average price as 22 USD/Ton (equal to 19,8 Euro/Ton) and take total registered area as 164,35 hectares and licensed registered area as 21,22 hectares, total value would be 292 Milton/Euro based on 14.714.925 tons x Euro 19,8 but operational costs was not included into this calculation.

RESULT: As already mentioned in the report, we have the following opinion and conviction which we now submit to the honorary Court: As compared to the geological resource reporting of the calcite outcrops available in the registered areas with access numbers 3074415 and 32499125, in the visible asset determination made according to the surface area, calcite resource was given as 14.714.925 tons based on a calcite thickness of 30 meters; average price range was determined to be 20-24 USD/Ton; if we take the average price as 22 USD/Ton (equal to 19,8 Euro/Ton) and take total registered area as 164,35 hectares and licensed registered area as 21,22 hectares, total value would be 292 Milton/Euro based on 14.714.925 tons x Euro 19,8 but operational costs was not included into this calculation.

(Signed)

Dr. Hasan KARADENİZ

Sworn Judicial Financial Expert Witness

(Signed)

Sefa ÖNTÜRK

Mining Engineer

(Official seal and signature)

TRUE COPY

01.01.2021

Polat TEKİN

Çeşme Civil Court of First Instance

Editor

İşbu T.C. 'den m'ye tercümenin
dairemiz yeminli çevirmenlerinden
tarafından aslına uygun olarak
tercüme edildiğini onaylım.

T.C.
BEŞİKTAŞ 29.
NOTERLİĞİ

ÇEVİRME - TERCÜME

TERCÜMAN BEYANI:

Tercüme edilmek üzere bana verilen Türkçe dilindeki belgeyi İngilizce diline tam ve doğru olarak çevirdiğimi beyan ederim.

YEMİNLİ TERCÜMAN

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Bu tercümenin yukarıdaki adreste bulunan noterliğimiz Yeminli Tercümanı **OSMAN FERHAT DEMİRHAN** tarafından Türkçe dilinden İngilizce diline tercüme edildiğini onaylarım. İki Haziran ikibinyirmibir, Çarşamba günü 02/06/2021

BEŞİKTAŞ 29. NOTERİ
Müjgan GÜNAYDIN ÖZCANYerine
İmzaya Yetkili Başkatip
Burak KOÇ